

IMPROVEMENT OF THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE ACTIVITIES OF CRIME PREVENTION SERVICES OF THE PUBLIC SECURITY DEPARTMENT OF THE MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS DURING THE REFORMS OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract.

The article discusses the improvement of the legal framework for the activities of crime prevention services of the Public Security Department of the Ministry of Internal Affairs during the reforms of New Uzbekistan, and offers suggestions and recommendations for more effective organization of these activities.

Keywords: Ministry of Internal Affairs, Public Security Department, Crime Prevention Services, crime prevention activities, legal framework.

In our country, protecting human rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests, maintaining public order and ensuring public safety, combating offenses, and generally preventing offenses, identifying and eliminating their causes and enabling conditions, identifying individuals prone to committing offenses, and raising legal awareness and legal culture in society are the main tasks of the crime prevention services of the Public Security Department of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. Their crime prevention activities play an important role in ensuring normal, peaceful, and tranquil living standards in the social life of society. In order for these entities to effectively carry out their service activities, specific regulatory and legal frameworks and appropriate conditions are being created in our country during the current period of reforms in New Uzbekistan.

It should be noted that during the period of reforms in New Uzbekistan, the adoption of a number of normative legal acts aimed at fundamentally improving the activities of internal affairs bodies in preventing offenses, combating crime, maintaining public order and ensuring public safety, adopted on the basis of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-4947 of February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [1] "Strategy of Actions in Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic

Specifically, in order to ensure the implementation of this Decree, it is necessary to recognize the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-2833 of March 14, 2017, "On Measures to Further Improve the System of Crime Prevention and Combating Crime" [2] as one of the important steps in improving the legal foundations of the activities of the crime prevention services of the Department of Public Safety of the Ministry of Internal Affairs at the beginning of the reforms of New Uzbekistan. The reason is that this decision serves to improve the cooperation of crime prevention subjects and create a more effective system for the implementation of crime and crime prevention.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5005 of April 10, 2017, "On Measures to Fundamentally Enhance the Effectiveness of Internal Affairs Bodies, Strengthen Their Responsibility for Ensuring Public Order, Reliable Protection of the Rights,

Freedoms, and Legitimate Interests of Citizens" [3] defines the actual tasks of fundamentally reforming, improving, and preventing the activities of internal affairs bodies, including the crime prevention services of the Department of Public Safety of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. In particular, in accordance with this Decree, the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan twice a year reports on the state of prevention and prevention of offenses of the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Jokargy Kenes of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the Kengashes of people's deputies of the city of Tashkent and the regions quarterly select the minister of internal affairs of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the heads of the main departments of internal affairs of the city of Tashkent and the Tashkent region and the internal affairs

The adoption of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-2896 of April 18, 2017, "On Measures to Fundamentally Improve the Activities of Offenses Prevention Units of Internal Affairs Bodies" [4] also serves to strengthen the legal foundations of the offenses prevention services of the Department of Public Security of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, increase the effectiveness of their activities and further improve their management. In particular, this resolution provides for:

- establishing a qualitatively new order of activity of the republican, middle and lower levels of crime prevention units, clearly defining and demarcating their main tasks, functions and responsibilities, preventing the imposition of non-specific functions on prevention inspectors;

- organization of preventive work in close cooperation with the population, citizens' self-government bodies and other institutions of civil society, focusing this work primarily on ensuring early prevention of offenses, raising legal culture in society, instilling in citizens respect for the law and an attitude of intolerance to any manifestation of violations of the law;

- development of the system of work with minors and youth aimed at their upbringing in the spirit of love for the Motherland, patriotism, respect for national and universal values, protection of the younger generation from the ideas of terrorism, religious extremism, violence and cruelty;

- strengthening the personal responsibility of prevention inspectors for the proper fulfillment of the duties assigned to them, including the establishment of systematic public reporting on their activities, eliminating cases of their superficial attitude to the problems that concern the population;

- introduction of effective criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of the activities of prevention inspectors, taking into account, first of all, public opinion, citizens' satisfaction with the results of their activities and the level of interaction with the population;

- the most important task of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its territorial divisions is the implementation of the main directions for improving the effectiveness of crime prevention, such as the widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies in this sphere, raising the level of knowledge and professional training of prevention inspectors, creating decent working conditions for them, providing them with official accommodation in the territory directly assigned to them, introducing mechanisms of material incentives for the effectiveness of the tasks assigned to them.

Also, by this decision, the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, khokimiyats of regions and the city of Tashkent were instructed to provide preventive inspectors with official accommodation in their assigned territory by January 1, 2018.

It can be said that as a result of the decrees and resolutions adopted during the ongoing reforms, effective work is being carried out in the field of crime prevention by the internal affairs bodies. In particular, in order to ensure the proximity of the internal affairs bodies to the population and to create convenience for citizens in settlements located far from the internal affairs departments (departments), an additional 175 city departments (divisions) and 824 base points of internal affairs were created.[5] The number of prevention inspectors serving at the lowest level of crime prevention has been increased from 5,867 to 6,969.[6] Currently, as a result of the reforms implemented in this area, the number of prevention inspectors is 10,132 [7], and certain work is underway to consolidate this area with experienced personnel.

The Regulation "On the Support Point of Internal Affairs Bodies," approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures to Fundamentally Improve the Activities of Offenses Prevention Units of Internal Affairs Bodies" of April 18, 2017, further strengthened the legal status, organization and management of the activities of the crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies.

Furthermore, as a logical continuation of the aforementioned reforms, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-6196 "On Measures to Raise the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies to a Qualitatively New Level in the Field of Ensuring Public Safety and Combating Crime" [8] of March 26, 2021, directly contributes to the improvement of the legal framework for the activities of crime prevention services of the Department of Public Safety of the Ministry of Internal Affairs during the reforms of New Uzbekistan. In particular, this Decree defines the following as fundamentally new mechanisms for organizing the activities of internal affairs bodies in ensuring public safety, preventing offenses and combating crime, strengthening law and order and legality in our [9] country through the establishment of effective activities of internal affairs bodies from the lowest level to the republican level and the introduction of modern methods of work, ensuring peace and tranquility of the population:

- solving problems related to crime prevention and combating crime directly on the ground by identifying the causes of crime and eliminating them in the context of each mahalla, family and individual;

- allocating each district, city and mahalla to categories based on the state of crime in the regions and attracting all necessary forces and means to eliminate "crime hotspots" in cooperation with khokimiyats, sectors and the public;

- Ensuring peace and stability in our country through the introduction of integrated management and continuous control mechanisms based on the "republic - region - district - mahalla" system, effective coordination of the activities of internal affairs and other state bodies to ensure public safety;

- creating a modern image of internal affairs officers, increasing their responsibility and professional potential, developing the necessary skills to combat new forms of crime, and achieving complete digitalization of the sphere.

At the same time, this Decree defines the phased establishment of mahalla law enforcement centers on the basis of support points of the internal affairs bodies, as well as:

- mahalla law enforcement is considered the main subordinate link in ensuring public safety in the region, preventing offenses and combating crime;

- organization of the coordinated activities of the relevant sectoral services of the internal affairs bodies of the region and the National Guard and other state bodies on the basis of the mahalla law enforcement center;

- it was determined that the task of systematic organization and coordination of work on ensuring public safety, preventing offenses and combating crime by the mahalla law enforcement agency will be assigned to the prevention inspector.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 29, 2021, No. UP-27 "On Approving the Concept of Public Safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Measures for its Implementation" [10] also plays a special role in the further improvement and strengthening of the legal status of the crime prevention services of the Department of Public Safety of the Ministry of Internal Affairs in the process of large-scale reforms being carried out in our country today, as well as in ensuring a peaceful and tranquil life of the population, forming a culture of lawfulness and Specifically, this Decree defines the main tasks of the Department of Public Safety and defines one of its main tasks as ensuring the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of crime prevention, organizing work on the social adaptation of persons under preventive accounting and administrative supervision, as well as preventing offenses among minors and young people, especially their unorganized part, by effectively organizing targeted educational and preventive measures, ensuring the execution of sentences not related to imprisonment, monitoring the behavior of persons under probation, organizing work

Also, in order to effectively ensure public safety in the mahalla, the tasks assigned to the prevention inspectors of the internal affairs bodies were optimized by this Decree, and the involvement of prevention inspectors in activities not related to their tasks and areas of activity, as well as unjustified interference in their activities were prohibited. At the same time, starting from September 1, 2024, it was determined that only employees with higher legal education will be appointed to the positions of senior prevention inspectors of the internal affairs bodies of the city of Tashkent, and from September 1, 2025, other territorial internal affairs bodies, and a number of opportunities were provided for prevention inspectors, and in the "Concept of Public Safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [11], approved by this Decree, it was determined that the public safety system consists of entities that ensure public safety and participate in it, and the Ministry of Internal

It should be noted that today, the Department of Public Safety of the Ministry of Internal Affairs' crime prevention services provide effective services in maintaining public order and ensuring public safety in residential areas, organizing crime prevention, raising the legal awareness and culture of the population, creating a way of life that fully corresponds to the way of life, spirituality, values and mentality of our people.

However, it should be noted that since the emergence of humanity in the world to the present day, just as humanity has taken a step towards development, in other words, society has always been in development, it is a fact that the types of offenses are increasing, improving, developing and becoming more complex with time. Therefore, the effective implementation of crime prevention and the fight against crime on an ongoing basis is one of the most pressing tasks of every era.

Based on these considerations, it can be said that raising the effectiveness of the activities and work of the crime prevention services of the Department of Public Safety of the Ministry of Internal Affairs to a new level is a modern requirement. Based on this requirement, it is advisable for them to carry out activities aimed at maintaining public order and ensuring public safety, preventing violations, eliminating the causes and conditions that contributed to the

commission of violations, based on laws and regulatory legal acts, effectively using forms and methods of activity, as well as official powers.

In conclusion, it can be said that in the 21st century, which is called the modern information age, that is, in a time when modern information and communication technologies are rapidly developing, at the same time, modern threats are widespread in the world's social life, in other words, as today's world society develops, the types of offenses are also developing, complicating and improving, in accordance with the development of the social life of society, one of the urgent tasks is to improve both the legal foundations of the activities of the crime prevention services of the Department of

When organizing these works, it is advisable, first and foremost, to study existing problems in this area, conduct a systematic analysis of laws and regulatory legal acts related to the field of activity, and develop appropriate proposals and recommendations for filling existing gaps based on modern requirements. In other words, today, when important reforms are being implemented in our country to develop a democratic state governed by the rule of law and a free civil society, it would not be an exaggeration to say that the widespread and serious development of the legal foundations of the activities of the crime prevention services of the Department of Public Security of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the introduction of effective forms of legal norms into our lives are the demands of today.

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